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FEMaLe

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of 1 Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 About the Project and this document

The Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning (FEMaLe) project will bring the cohesion of state-of-the-art technologies, genetics, biomarker testing together to personalize the early risk prediction of endometriosis with an aim to ensure individualized intervention, and to build knowledge for prognostic prevention by the identification of subtypes of endometriosis.

Dissemination of policy examination and production, innovation action results and publication of data and products is overseen by WP9 and is supported by the project's Advisory Board members, incorporating respect to protection of intellectual property. Processes, protocols and guidance to facilitate dissemination and exploitation are quantified and detailed in this document in regard to the dissemination, exploitation, communication and synergies strategy.

This document outlines the Dissemination and Communication plans for the FEMaLe project to structure and coordinate activities and efforts to ensure the intended outcomes, and that the specific objectives of the project are met. This includes effectively reaching and engaging a wide audience, including clusters such as females diagnosed with endometriosis, health maintenance organizations, surgeons, clinical workers and others, across all project activities. For people with endometriosis, which are arguably the largest direct beneficiaries of project activities, the project will “spread a word” across Europe to attract as many people into using project deliverables as well as for health care professionals, to facilitate the project outcomes in their everyday practice.

In order to achieve this, the FEMaLe Communication & Dissemination team will develop a strategic approach, as well as materials and tools to be used by all consortium partners across project activities, considering the following aspects (but not limited to):

- ✓ Careful and detailed audience mapping analysis to ensure all stakeholders are identified as well as their needs/expectations concerning the FEMaLe project
- ✓ Complete Dissemination & Communication assessment taking into account the full stakeholder journey, with channels, tactics and campaigns (both online & offline) to bring the FEMaLe right in front of diverse audiences
- ✓ Critical KPIs to be tracked and benchmarked to prove the overall value of our dissemination efforts and set further guidance regarding communication, community building & exploitation.

1.2 About the strategy

The dissemination and exploitation of the project's results are one of the fundamental components of the FEMaLe project. Therefore, a clear plan and strategy are developed for this purpose. The planned activities and results will be disseminated throughout the life span of the project. In this context, this document is meant to be used as a strategic plan for all promotional activities for the project by the partners. As a living document responding to new development and opportunities, updates of the dissemination and communication plan can be made upon approval by the project coordinator / Consortium during the implementation process of the project. Our envisaged Dissemination and Communication Strategy is tailored to contribute to the achieving of the overall project goal, reaching the defined target groups and making sure that the key messages of the project are disseminated.

In this regard, the objectives of the dissemination activities will be focused on:

- ✓ Promoting broad visibility of the project's efforts and disseminate its results
- ✓ Establishing liaisons with related initiatives, organizations and projects both within the social media context and beyond as appropriate,
- ✓ Creating and maintaining the project web platform and appropriate communication channels and dissemination tools,
- ✓ Participating in and organizing specific (including remote events and webinars) for increased and effective liaisons, dissemination of information and engagement of key stakeholders in the social media ecosystem.

The strategy is consistent with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, ensuring there is a clear pathway for effective deployment, knowledge transfer and exploitation of results. This Deliverable is structured as follows: Chapter 2 will define the dissemination and communication plan, including the target groups which this project will engage with and provide key messages it will convey to them. It will also present the underlying strategy that was developed, describing the tools that will be employed to reach the defined target groups, both graphic and digital materials. Chapter 3 will define the Exploitation strategy, by defining the FEMaLe exploitation areas as per project's proposal.

2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

In the last century, the most important updates in healthcare services economics were related to artificial intelligence, machine learning and augmented reality. As the society has developed certain reservations towards the modernization of treatments that include state-of-the-art technology, FEMaLe project will communicate with simple, yet explanatory messages, to increase the awareness upon the adoption of advanced technologies in the sector.

For that purpose, FEMaLe project will make a significant contribution towards the smart integration of digital tools, mainly in local healthcare communities of the metropolitan area. Plans to disseminate and exploit the outcomes of FEMaLe are in line with the EC's Guidelines for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results in Horizon 2020. Within WP9, activities will be undertaken to identify and engage with the full range of agents of the healthcare and citizens.

2.1 Dissemination plan

The dissemination plan describes the actions envisioned to build awareness of the project results and deliverables, creating understanding of them, and aiming for action among the relevant target audience. Realizing FEMaLe's overall vision requires making relevant target audiences aware of the project's findings, outcomes, and its concept, as well as to facilitate reuse/uptake as appropriate.

The objectives of the dissemination plan are as follows:

- ✓ To set up the information dissemination mechanisms and priorities of FEMaLe,
- ✓ To establish, maintain and grow a community around FEMaLe in coordination with the stakeholder analysis,
- ✓ To create visibility and promote the work and results for target stakeholders by producing promotional material and information campaigns,
- ✓ To disseminate project and outcomes to the widest possible community through various channels and instruments. External participation and knowledge sharing will be encouraged through networking activities and events aimed at increasing the impact potential and enriching the contribution to the project,
- ✓ To liaise with relevant other EU, national and international initiatives to maximize the impact.

The Dissemination plan comprises the following:

- ✓ Objectives, procedures, and specific activities for communication, dissemination and securement of the project's synergies.
- ✓ Timeline, infographics, and Gantt's for dissemination activities.
- ✓ Analysis of risk and possibilities to prevent and solve.
- ✓ Procedure of project's visual identity by which each activity run within FEMaLe will mention and display EU emblem and EU funding, in compliance with the disclaimer.
- ✓ Internal communication plan.
- ✓ Targeted audience.
- ✓ Communication channels. It is primarily aimed to broaden the communication and dissemination channels of the project. It will be targeted their alignment to the specific features of each partner country.
- ✓ Models of good practices for ensuring the knowledge transfer to the stakeholders, policymakers, citizens, rural and urban networks, healthcare clusters, advisory services, research community, and public.

2.1.1 Key measures for the project's visibility

Measures that will be taken to ensure a maximized visibility of the project:

1. Development of a clear and comprehensive strategy within the dissemination plan
2. Appointment of a dedicated steering committee & task force – Communication team responsible for coordinating communication & dissemination activities and animation of respective partners
3. Development of an attractive project's visual identity and branding with following deliverables:
 - Visual style guide (logo, typeface, Consortium logo)
 - Templates: Word, PPT, notebook
 - Digital and print promotional material (posters, leaflets, brochures, roll up banners)

4. Development of materials supporting external & internal communication:
 - Project's web platform
 - Social media banners
 - Infographics
 - Newsletter
5. Establishment of organized group of motivated promoters (social media influencers and people within scientific community) for advocacy and PR activities (generation of online network platform, establishment of working groups, identification and utilization of multiplier events)
6. Development of Trust and Transparency Ecosystem (2TE) animated by motivated practitioners
7. Organization of bi-monthly small-scale events (roundtables, webinars and similar)
8. Participation in fairs, conferences and Congresses (keynote speeches) with exposure elements (booth design)
9. Support and fostering of project spin-offs to consolidate the project and build upon its results
10. Organization of annual campaigns taking place in partner countries
11. Implementation of monitoring and evaluation system to ensure an alignment with project objectives and swift adjustments based on empirical data

2.1.2 Target groups

The FEMaLe communication & dissemination needs to be tailored to the specific needs of the different target audiences of the project. Defining the target groups is a key component, and vital for the dissemination strategy. This section identifies the 9 target audiences of the project:

1. People with endometriosis
 - a. Special attention within this group will be paid to LGBT individuals
2. Healthcare providers:
 - a. General practitioners
 - b. Gynecologists
 - c. Radiologists
 - d. Surgeons
3. Health maintenance organizations
4. Research & academia:
 - a. Researchers & Top universities
5. Local authorities, investors & decision makers:
 - a. Policy makers & change makers
 - b. Entrepreneurs & start-ups
6. General public
 - a. Civil society
7. Mass media & Industry

Each target group has its own sphere of communication. FEMaLe's approach will be aimed at various groups, with the primary audiences shown in the table below. We will also define the priority level to engaging these groups, considering their relevance to the project and its scope of work, as well as their interest in FEMaLe.

2.1.3 Key messages

The key messages should focus the project goals, project results, project activities and other defined in a clear manner that should contain the most relevant information.

Key messages are an integral part of the dissemination strategy as they will encourage the stakeholders to participate, and they will be adapted to each target group.

See some examples provided in the *Table 1: Key messages for FEMaLe key target audience group, and their priority*. These examples can be updated at any time accordingly taking into consideration the specific target groups' needs.

Table 2.1.3.1: Key messages for FEMaLe key target audience group, and their priority

Target group	Key message	Priority
People with endometriosis	FEMaLe project will help with the diagnosis and treatment of endometriosis. Clinical Decision Support and self-management tools will be developed to help patients become their own endometriosis specialists, ultimately preventing the development of chronic pain problems and reducing the negative physical, psychological and social symptoms while improving the overall quality of life in people with endometriosis.	High
Healthcare providers	Increasing volume and sophistication of collected healthcare data will provide an opportunity for earlier identification of disease, drive future diagnoses and help a greater number of patients receive proper care and treatment.	High
Health maintenance organizations	FEMaLe project will develop the Clinical Decision Support tools that will decrease the costs of treatment of the endometriosis, as well as improved outcomes.	High
Research & Academia	FEMaLe brings the state-of-the-art technology into the scientific disease research. FEMaLe deliverables will provide insight into possible new drug targets or drug repurposing opportunities.	High
Local authorities & Decision makers	FEMaLe project is shedding the light towards the key factors contributing the growth of the market. Find out how FEMaLe can influence your policy.	Medium
General public	Diagnosing endometriosis has just become easier and more available for people worldwide. FEMaLe project is enabling the decision making between you and your doctor. Find out about the tools that will help you with your endometriosis diagnose and self-management.	Medium
Mass media & Industry	Find more information about the right tools to support your endometriosis treatment decision making. If you are interested in endometriosis treatment, keep an eye on FEMaLe to update your audience about the latest technologies, products & services that will reinvent the health decision making.	Medium - Low

Table 2.1.3.2: Target audiences and the respective topics for relevant key messages

Target Audience	Topics for key messages
Internal stakeholders	Project status, Project activities, Issues identified, Project results
External stakeholders	Project activities, Project results
Others	Project activities, Project results

The key message to be developed to each specific target group will be focusing on the 1) length of the message and 2) balance of the information.

A clear overview of the targeted institutions or individuals will ensure a more strategic and effective approach for example: sending invitations for webinars, information gathering, growing a community, dissemination of results and similar. The Communication Team will create the Relevant Stakeholders Lists and ask partners to provide information contacts of target institutions and persons, always taking into consideration the GDPR regulation. This list will be continuously updated throughout the project.

Image 2.1.3.1: An example of Key Stakeholders in Denmark identified and stratified by using Miro.

2.1.4 Key Performance Indicators

Dissemination is a key activity with strong synergy to multiple tasks across the project. Synergistic and complementary focus group - Communication team comprised of relevant appointed persons from TIEF, AU, EQUIP, and WBS will deliver an attractive and effective communication and ensure strong coordination across the consortium. It is recognized that a specific challenge is to effectively reach a wide pool of people with endometriosis across Europe. The synergies with ongoing partner activities, as well as the project web platform will strongly be leveraged for this.

The communication and dissemination activities will be monitored and evaluated to assess their impact on a regular basis and adjust where needed.

The following table presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which have been set to assess the progress of the FEMaLe communication efforts. They have been defined in accordance to the main project deliverables, and are addressing project exploitation and dissemination respectively.

Table 2.1.4.1: List of Key Performance Indicators and Target numbers

	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Target
Dissemination & Communication	Number of downloads of Lucy App on Google Play and App Store	2.000+
	Number of visits of fndingendometriosis.eu web platform	10.000+
	Number of tweets on Twitter	200+
	Number of posts on Facebook	200+
	Number of posts on LinkedIn	100+
	Number of blog posts produced by the Beneficiaries	12+
	Number of promotional videos disseminated on social media/website	10+
	Number of views on FEMaLe's YouTube channel	2.000+
	Number of awareness-raising and learning events to promote FEMaLe	20+
	Number of multipliers (projects, clusters, networks) engaged to promote FEMaLe	12+
Exploitation	Number of experts engaged in scientific developments	200+
	Number of scientific developments	25+
	Number of citizen-driven developments	100+
	Number of business-driven developments	25+
	Number of facilitators engaged to promote FEMaLe, incl. task force	50+

To measure the key indicators above, the following evaluation elements will be used:

- ✓ Google Analytics – to track and report the project website traffic
- ✓ Social Media Metrics – to track the engagement on Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter
- ✓ Communication reporting table:
 - Partners will report on the communication activities implemented in one single place:
 - The registries excel file, available on FEMaLe Correlate platform.
 - Partners should save evidence of the activities conducted (such as ppt presentations made, invitations, agenda, pictures, post on social media, etc.).

2.1.5 Dissemination Events

Dissemination events in social media and webinars / conferences will be important as they act as places to establish presence, build liaisons, and engage key stakeholders within the social media ecosystem.

An Excel table will be prepared by the Communication team and shared with all partners, to gather information concerning events, conferences, Congresses, webinars with details such as dates, contact info about the organizer and whether a partner will attend. This Excel Table will be a “live” document, updated according to the strategy of the Consortium and priority of events.

The events reported in this table will be announced on the project website, social media network, the project Blog and on the project Newsletter.

2.2 Communication plan

Communication is tasked with raising awareness of and stimulating interest in the project and its activities, involving specific measures for promoting the project itself and the results attained. As such, communication is highly complementary to dissemination and exploitation efforts. Communication will provide cross-project support for textual and graphic promotion, development, and maintenance of promotional material, etc.

The communication plan has the mission to reach out to a broader audience, beyond the FEMaLe core community, and this will be achieved by communicating well-tailored messages through effective channels to reach targeted audiences and to stimulate interaction between key external audiences and the project.

The objectives of the communication plan are as follows:

- ✓ Set up internal communication mechanisms among the partners within the Consortium,
- ✓ Support the external promotion of FEMaLe and its outcomes, managing the branding,
- ✓ Deliver top level messages about the project to all identified and relevant stakeholders,
- ✓ Raise awareness to non-specialized audiences of the added value of FEMaLe project,
- ✓ Increase awareness and interest about FEMaLe.

Communication campaigns will be designed and implemented throughout the project lifetime to efficiently build traction among the target audience, with a special focus on the FEMaLe population.

2.2.1 Key communication tools

Table 2.2.1.1: List of communication tools/channels with their description and purpose and their relevance for different types of audiences.

Tool/ Channel	Description and Purpose	Audience relevance						
		People with endometriosis	Healthcare providers	Health maintenance organizations	Research & academia	Local authorities, investors & decision makers	General public	Mass media & Industry
Project web platform	The project’s primary digital communication tool. Raising awareness of the project's goals & activities. Dedicated sections will be created for Clinical Decision Support tools, self-management portal.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Social media	Through Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube, FEMaLe will foster regular and timely conversations with key stakeholders, generate thought leadership and engagement, and maintain Ecosystem coherence. Reliable, respectable, high-quality content will be distributed in an intuitive, attractive and easy-to-understand format.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Digital + print promotional materials (posters, leaflets, brochures, posters, roll ups)	Promo material for the project and the accelerators stressing benefits for target audiences. The content will be developed having the receiving audience in mind.	✓	✓					✓	✓
Infographics	Infographics of current project status & findings. They will be developed having the scientific community in mind, to disseminate the results in a most comprehensive way.		✓	✓	✓	✓			
Blog	One of the more important communication instruments for knowledge transfer and capacity building. Blog posts will be developed by each partner to ensure the similar involvement of all partners and spreading the word about the project's scientific side.	✓	✓	✓	✓				
Newsletter	Key communication instrument, that will be sent by email to subscribers (an option for it will be made available in the project website) and shared on the FEMaLe's and partners' social networks with key information concerning the project's development, advancement and findings.	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
Promotional animated videos	A key promotional instrument for each Work package that will be used to promote the project in general, research and important work of each of the partners, benefits for each stakeholder and similar.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓

2.2.2 Visual identity

2.2.2.1 Color identity

The selection of the color identity of the project is crucial to ensure the dissemination of the correct message. In FEMaLe, the project’s color palette has been selected to be eye-catching and to communicate trust and health. The theme will represent the color of project coordinator Aarhus University, as well as the feminine side of the project by introduction of the light colors. Currently, the logo is comprised of only one color - AU-blue (Pantone 287), while the improved version will also incorporate the “endometriosis yellow”, as per the color palette below:

Image 2.2.2.1.1: Color palette with RGB and CMYK instructions for usage.

All the project partners are kindly requested to use the newly developed color palette for any graphics or color designs or backgrounds that will be used to communicate about FEMaLe. An email will be circulated among all the partners by the communication team with instructions on how to properly use the colors, the logos, and the project templates.

2.2.2.2 Logo

The logo plays a central role in the project’s visual identity. It aids recollection and recall, and it should be included in all external communications from the project.

The logo developed is clear, captures the attention of the public and communicates the main concepts of FEMaLe – a person connected with machines – a strong message of machine learning is communicated subconsciously.

Image 2.2.2.2.1: Initial version of the project logo.

The initial version displays the project's primary focus – people, while the symbiosis with machine (gears) is made in order to showcase the mutual work of people and technology towards achieving the project's goals. Acronym below is in a single font, using the font that is making the connection towards the project coordinator.

The official logo of the project is the first one that displays both the project's acronym and the graphic visual above.

Several versions of the logo (e.g., with different background or color coding) will be developed and made available to the project partners through the FEMaLe Correlate platform.

2.2.2.2.1 Usage

1. Partners should use their judgment to determine when to use which logo. One of the most crucial rules before the use of the logo is: "If you can't read it, you can't use it". The partners should ensure that they use the right size and resolution for each promotional activity and avoid pixilation.
2. Another general rule for partners is that the logo should never be altered in any way and it should never be rotated.
3. The partners must consider that every time that they use the FEMaLe logo, the following messages should be indirectly communicated to the partners:
 - Differentiation
 - Memorability
 - Persistence (durable)
 - Positivity (avoids negative connotations)
 - Originality

2.2.2.2.2 Usage with EU emblem

A copy of the EU emblem and a text stating that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 programme will be included in any dissemination material including the electronic ones. This emblem is available from the EU at the link: <http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/>. The EU emblem accompanied by the abovementioned text will be added as follows: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017562.

2.2.3 Digital and print promotional materials (posters, leaflets, brochures, posters, roll ups)

To ensure consistency of the project's visual identity, the communication team will prepare templates to be used universally for the preparation of presentations, press releases, etc. These templates will be shared through email communication and via the FEMaLe Correlate platform among all the partners.

2.2.3.1 Digital material

2.2.3.1.1 Word template

For the needs of the preparation of the project's deliverables, the deliverable template will be produced in an MS Word format applying the project style. The purpose of such template is to have a consistent and recognizable layout for the project's deliverables.

The initial version has been developed for the purposes of submitting deliverables, and looks as presented below:

The initial version cover page has eye-catching visuals that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, the name of the deliverable and the relevant Work Package, while at the bottom of the page there is a clear statement that the project has received funding from the EU along with the emblem of the EU as required in the Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement.

Image 2.2.3.1.1.1: Example of the initial Word template for deliverables, cover page.

The second page of the template includes a table with the document’s information and the document history.

Image 2.2.3.1.1.2: Example of the initial Word template for deliverables, second page.

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	Dx.x
DELIVERABLE TITLE	
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	
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The third page of the deliverable template is reserved for the table of contents and figures. The final page lists the documents’ references, while the document contains also a back cover with similar visuals. The first, second, and third page of the template remain static, do not change and contain only the information referred above. The footer of the template also contains the EU emblem and the project logo.

For the dissemination purposes, the original templates will be upgraded and redesigned. After the logo is improved, all deliverables will follow the new visual identity to offer a unified look.

2.2.3.1.2 PPT template

FEMaLe presentations are part of the different dissemination activities designed to support the consortium's dissemination efforts. The presentation template will be used in all events and meetings where the project results and activities are presented, and it was designed following the graphic identity guidelines to facilitate the recognition of the project. Initial version of PPT template has been developed for the purposes of each WP presenting their tasks, deliverables and milestones to the Consortium.

The first page of the deliverable template is a cover page with visuals along the lines of the rest of the deliverables and the overall visual identity. Project's logo is the most prominent on the cover, accompanied by the title, name of the deliverable and the relevant Work package, with a clear statement that the project has received funding from the EU along with the emblem of the EU as required in the Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement at the footer.

Image 2.2.3.1.2.1: Example of PPT template, initial version for deliverables, cover page.

The rest of the presentation template pages have a logo representing the FEMaLe project, while the rest is left blank to be filled with content.

The initial version of the PPT template will be improved in order to support the dissemination activities and presenting the project. The improved version will follow the new & improved visual identity to complete the brand.

Similar templates for the internal and external communication of the project will be designed, such as notebook template and other visual identity deliverables.

2.2.3.1.3 Print material

Print material is a very important promotional instrument when participating in events.

The most common items include brochures, posters and any other laid out paper-based resource. The project will prepare 4 sets (iterations) of each version to select the best one, once a year based on the project's development. Most of the PR material will be available as e-documents and printing will occur as required (e.g., for events, workshops, etc.).

The first set of material will primarily look at explaining the objectives of the project in a consistent manner, showing the potential achievements and impact; the second and third sets will show the more advanced results; and the fourth set will highlight the final results. If needed, these sets will be released with two or three different contents, tailored to each stakeholder category the project aims to reach.

The project will give primarily focus to digital promotional materials, since this is taking into account a minimum environmental impact. The use of printed materials will be considered for their impact, cost, and their environmental profile (recycled paper, non-petroleum ink, etc.) and only printed in case deemed necessary for participation in physical events.

2.2.4 FEMaLe web platform

The project website will be designed following the latest trends in website design with a focus on actively promoting the results on the home page with banners, and also providing great visibility to the impact achievements generated by the project activities.

Website will be designed with following in mind:

- a) Content will be fully organized within HTML guidelines to allow easy translation in almost limitless languages.
- b) Backbone architecture will be built with the latest Search Engine Optimization (SEO) system to outpace the 'search competition'.
- c) Web analytics tool will be placed to allow tracking and traffic reports.

Various tools will be deployed to ensure the dynamics of the website:

- a) Attractive headlines to easily identify what the website is about.
- b) Engaging 'pop-ups' with the viewer to suggest where to take the next step and to subscribe to the notifications systems (possibly RSS).
- c) Highly attractive layout yet with four areas only: Project, Resources, Challenges and Media.
- d) Social Media-oriented design (pictures, headlines, fonts, colors, layout).
- e) Social media live feeds.
- f) Integrated search tool with automatic key words and tags to allow quick access to targeted thematic.
- g) Testimonials.
- h) Frequently renewed content offer.

An initial mock-up of the website's home page is presented below. The initial version is delivered in M3, while a fully working web platform will be delivered in M6.

Image 2.2.4.1: Print screen of the current FEMaLe project's landing page.

FINDING ENDOMETRIOSIS USING MACHINE LEARNING

The FEMaLe project will build bridges across disciplines and sectors to translate genetic and epidemiological knowledge into clinical tools that support decision-making in terms of diagnosis and care aimed at both general practice and highly specialised endometriosis clinics – all via machine learning and artificial intelligence.

[FEMaLe digital legacy](#)

FEMaLe in News

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2.2.5 Social media

An intensive Social Media campaign is going to be launched by the FEMaLe project, leveraging the project's social media channels. This will be achieved by the project Communication Team through a specific's social media assets:

- ✓ Communication in other relevant H2020 projects,
- ✓ Professional graphic designers to provide images for attractive posts,
- ✓ Professional animated films making to create attractive video snippets for social media,
- ✓ Several physical activities allowing for attractive “in action” photographs to be shared on social media,
- ✓ Validated approach to connect with beneficiaries over social media and promote their own content for the purposes of promoting the project and back-linking
- ✓ Live tweeting and use of the Twitter wall during events to “involve” those who are not present,
- ✓ Live tweeting at progress meetings
- ✓ Live streaming on Instagram during events to spread the word about the event
- ✓ Instagram feed showcasing the project, the people involved and cross-posting with influencers

FEMaLe will create and maintain actively its presence in several social media channels, with special focus on Twitter and LinkedIn as they have proven to be the most effective tools when engaging with scientific communities, while Facebook and Instagram will be utilized to engage the people with endometriosis and other wide audiences. These online channels will help promote new publications and participation in different kinds of events, while interacting with our target audience.

To ensure a successful social media presence, the following actions will be put into motion:

- ✓ Appointment of a dedicated Social media team responsible for posting and engagement over social media networks
- ✓ Appointment of social media experts who will support the Social media team by analytics screening and best practice guidance
- ✓ Utilization of animated videos to be shared via “social media influencers” page to help them become “brand ambassadors”
- ✓ Creation of audience personas (trending and influencing groups) to drive the personalization of messages and content
- ✓ Optimization of partners' social media presence and networks towards the community building
- ✓ Develop interviews, questionnaires, online reviews etc. to follow the social media presence and feedback

2.2.6 General media

This communication activity refers to the development of newspaper articles, external blog posts, and online articles at selected publications.

The following media strategy will be adopted, which will allow for a regular publication of press releases / blogs:

- ✓ The articles and press releases will be developed by the core consortium.
- ✓ If needed
- ✓ If needed, the partners speaking the language should translate the developed articles and press releases into their local language and release them to their country/local media channels and lists of journalists/contacts. Partners are free to adapt the articles as reasonably convenient. Through the local efforts from all partners it will be possible to achieve a wide European outreach.
- ✓ All partners will be helped if needed to translate the developed articles and press releases into their local language (if applicable) and release them to their country/local media channels and lists of journalists/contacts. Partners are free to adapt the articles as reasonably convenient. Through the local efforts from all partners, it will be possible to achieve a wide European outreach.
- ✓ Once results are available, the news will be success story oriented.

When the need will arise for dissemination of project results and information, press releases will be made by the communication team and distributed to a certain number of media channels and platforms, to amplify the impact and visibility of the project.

2.2.6.1 *How to write a good press release and/or article*

To start:

- ✓ Create a good title to spark attention
- ✓ Start with the conclusions to catch the reader's interest and describe your story in a few paragraphs, each telling a different point – use facts and figures
- ✓ Answer the main questions: Who? Why? What? Where? When?
- ✓ Add information in the format of quotes (one or two)
- ✓ Make it under one page

To close:

- ✓ Add the project logo and a relevant photo/image
- ✓ Provide the EU funding information (see Visual Identity)
- ✓ Don't forget to add the project website and social media
- ✓ Add your contact information
- ✓ Add a nice subject line in the email

2.2.6.2 *Alliance partners*

Besides the key stakeholders of the entire healthcare value chain outreach to be engaged in the project's implementation with a variety of partially structured role, other organisations from this value chain will be invited to engage as Alliance partners to develop as beacons to increase the project's visibility.

2.2.6.3 *Accompanying measures*

The consortium ambition is to ensure the expected project legacy beyond the project primary targeted audience. To add to this, a series of accompanying measures have been projected and are key elements of the Communication strategy. The plan details post-project developments and is supported by the same resources planned for dissemination, developing complementary activities.

The key drivers for the DeoRC strategy are motivated and committed partners that are assigned to lead specific post-project developments, a clear and shared vision (plan), materialized by an agreement between partners (2020-2024).

The DeoRC steering Committee is set to develop beyond 2024 with the adequate resources. Partners' resources are identified and assigned to the tasks with cost advantages (economies of scale) that they obtain through synergies with on-going projects and activities.

The Internet-based platforms will reach a users' critical mass generated by all the activities during the project duration that will afford self-sustainability beyond the project lifetime. Members of the Communication focus group will develop together multiplication-oriented activities to ensure the targeted audience is encouraged to use the project result:

- a) Mainstreaming via dynamic digital communication (website, social media pages, email subscriptions, etc.).
- b) Presenting and pilot testing successful case-studies in realistic and practical environment in partners' events (open days, conferences, webinars, etc.).
- c) Gamifying storytelling and narratives with attractive digital tools in events.
- d) Linking and leveraging systematically with existing and related projects in which project results meet the project's needs.
- e) Triggering collaborative work projects in which the project's results are used (research, pilots, training, learning mobilities, etc.).
- f) Sustainability mechanisms between the consortium's partners:
 - a. Bilateral or multilateral transnational meetings triggered by other activities and projects.
 - b. Four bilateral or multilateral teleconferences.
 - c. Trimestral checkpoints (state of the affairs) and reporting.
 - d. Continuous updating of all Internet-based tools.
 - e. Continuous dynamic activity of all results listed hereafter.

2.3 Dissemination and Communication Action Plan

The action plan is outlined according to the timeline of key results to be communicated. This timeline includes the information related to public deliverables and some milestones which are relevant to communicate along the project lifespan.

Table 2.3.1: Gantt chart of activities length and repetition within the project timeline

	2021												2022												2023												2024													
Task name	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48		
Website																																																		
Social Media																																																		
Newsletter																																																		
Blogs																																																		
Press Release																																																		
Animated video																																																		
Promotional Materials																																																		
Media																																																		
Exploitation																																																		
	*Table will be updated accordingly.																																																	

Main points of the action plan:

- ✓ The communication activities are led by the Communication team (focus group) with a contribution from all partners.
- ✓ The WP Leaders (core consortium) have the responsibility of contributing to the creation of content related to their WP activities, to be communicated in the various channels.
- ✓ All partners should prepare their communication activities according to the action plan. All partners play a crucial role in communicating the project at a local, national, and European level. Thus, it is important that they are aware of the timeline of key results to be communicated, as well as of the set of communication tools made available. The communication tools and channels, as well as the promotional materials planned, support the FEMaLe consortium in reaching out to the target stakeholders with the maximum impact.

The following division of responsibilities has been defined in relation to the communication and dissemination activities:

Table 2.3.2: List of deliverables and partners responsible for their production/contribution

Deliverable	Partner
Website design & development	WBS
Website content	WP Leaders + WBS (consultative role)
Blog content	Each WP leader per 1 blog
Blog publishing	Communication team
Social media content	Communication team + WP leaders
Social media publishing and engagement	Communication team
Newsletter	WBS (design) + WP leaders (content)
Promotional materials design & production	WBS
Promotional materials content	WP leaders
Animated videos production	WBS
Animated videos story boards & content	Each WP leader per 1 animated video
Media presence	Media: WP Leaders (all partners encouraged to diffuse)

2.4 Synergies with other projects and initiatives

The consortium will join forces and create synergies with projects and initiatives related to the topic of the FEMaLe project. For this purpose, and in order to maximize resources and leverage the partners' well-established network of contacts, partners will be asked to indicate which relevant networks and initiatives they are member of.

These synergies may result in the following activities:

- ✓ Cross promotion of open calls, activities, and events,
- ✓ Participation in events and conferences,
- ✓ Knowledge sharing.

2.4.1 Miscellaneous developments

Table 2.4.1.1: List of National/International Research Initiatives with their descriptions, potential uptakes and partners leading the connection.

National/International RI	Description	Potential uptake	Partners
Region Stockholm – Agenda Wellbeing	Modeling, simulation, demonstration, stakeholder engagement in formulating and implementing a cross-sectorial governance system for taking human development as the driver for regional development.	User involvement as driver for development of new tools and technologies (WP4-8).	KTH (P9)
EIT Health – POSITIVE	Data management and device management of a support platform for frail elderly people.	Data management and management of a platform to support vulnerable groups (WP2).	KTH (P9)
QBOL under the FP7 program. Project ID: 226482.	Development of a new diagnostic tool using DNA barcoding to identify quarantine organisms in support of plant health.	Experience with developing new diagnostic tools using genomic data (WP4).	KTH (P9)
NIHR HTA 2013-20 "PRE-EMPT"	Preventing Recurrence of Endometriosis by Means of long acting Progestogen Therapy	Prevention of endometriosis (WP5).	UOXF (P6) UEDIN (P17)
NIHR HTA 2020-25 "ESPrIT2"	A multi-centre randomized controlled trial to determine the effectiveness of laparoscopic treatment of isolated superficial peritoneal endometriosis for the management of chronic pelvic pain in women.	Management of chronic pelvic pain in women (WP8).	UOXF (P6) UEDIN (P17)
Lifelong Learning: InGPinQI [2012] 1-P11-Leo05-11473	Innovative Lifelong Learning of European General Physicians in Quality Improvement Supported By Information Technology	Insights in production of e-learning materials attractive to general practitioners (WP9).	EQuIP (P4)

2.4.2 H2020 developments

Table 2.4.2.1: List of H2020 projects with their descriptions, potential uptakes and partners responsible for connection.

National/International RI	Description	Potential uptake	Partners
Ageing with elegans under the H2020 program. Project ID: 633589.	Validating C. elegans health span model for better understanding factors causing health and disease, to develop evidence-based prevention, diagnostic, therapeutic and other strategies.	Experience with comprehensive models for revealing factors causing health and disease to be used for better prevention, diagnostics, and therapies (WP5).	AU (P1)
FundaMentalHM under the H2020 program. Project ID: 837180.	Innovative methods for better estimation of Fundamental Health Metrics associated with Mental disorders and other general medical conditions.	Innovative methods for developing complex metrics (WP4-WP5).	AU (P1)
PROFID under the H2020 program. Project ID: 847999.	Implementation of personalized risk prediction and prevention of sudden cardiac death after myocardial infarction.	Implementation of predictive tools, based on personalized risk scores (WP4).	AU (P1)
SMILE under the H2020 program. Project ID: 690227.	Self-management, information and computing technology, and lifestyle education in women with a history of gestational diabetes.	Digital self-management program for women (WP8).	AU (P1)
SNIFFPHONE. Project ID: ZD2015/20030.	Smart Phone for Disease Detection from Exhaled Breath	Mobile Health App for rapid detection of disease (WP5).	RTU (P8)
EU, IMI2-2016-10-03C (6.48 mil. EUR) 2018-21.	Models of Endometriosis Pain. P Saunders (WP leader).	Personalised medicine (WP2).	UEDIN (P17)

2.4.3 Relevant organizations

World Endometriosis Society - The World Endometriosis Society (WES) advances evidence-based standards and innovations for education, advocacy, clinical care, and research in endometriosis, adenomyosis, and related disorders, in collaboration with its stakeholders and global partners to improve the lives of all affected women and their families.
[WES website](#)

Cochrane - Cochrane is an international network but with headquarters in the UK, it is registered as a not-for-profit organization. Cochrane is for anyone interested in using high-quality information to make health decisions. Whether you are a doctor or nurse, patient or carer, researcher or funder, Cochrane evidence provides a powerful tool to enhance your healthcare knowledge and decision making.
[Cochrane website](#)

Endometriosis.org - Endometriosis.org is the global platform which links all stakeholders in endometriosis. It facilitates collaboration and information sharing between women with endometriosis, physicians, scientists, and others interested in the disease.
[Endometriosis.org website](#)

Endometriosis UK – Endometriosis UK is a small organization from United Kingdom that provide vital support services, reliable information and a community for those affected by endometriosis. In their words, they are a “very small organisation, striving for big results.”
[Endometriosis UK website](#)

3 EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

Under Work Package 9 FEMaLe's Heritage Action Agenda will be co-created. This actionable and deployable agenda incorporates an action plan, describes and structures a strategy to facilitate and encourage the exploitation of the project outputs and ensure the sustainability after the project's scope. The consortium will co-develop this legacy plan exploring multiple pathways to gather support for the sustainability of the project results.

The action plan includes a task force of 50 multipliers distributed in all participating countries. It details tailored exploitation plans including target markets and agents of the health and care arena, e.g. market analysis and exploitation plan (segments, strategy), performance based price elasticity assessment, market access barriers including IPR financial business case analysis, e.g. business models and exploitation plans aimed at target markets to illustrate results of the project, and to show how they can innovatively benefit the health and care spheres in a commercially feasible ecosystem services offering.

A Research Innovation Action exploitation plan and a Citizen and Open Science exploitation plan are embedded in the actionable and deployable agenda. Results will be presented at international exhibitions in the reference arena e.g. health and care and related spheres. All in all, the Heritage Action Agenda encourages the use of the project results during the project scope and beyond.

The main aim of exploitation in FEMaLe is to ensure the sustainability of the project's results beyond the project end and to demonstrate how the project has influenced the EU healthcare landscape.

Exploitation includes:

1. Financial exploitation, building products, projects, or services based on the project results
2. Research & Innovation development, by engaging new projects (EU-funded or sponsored by other sources), based on the experiences gained in the project
3. Education, e.g. courses, at the university level or in continuing education, etc.
4. Community-building around the topics of the project, raising awareness for the addressed problems and the proposed solutions
5. Knowledge transfer, from academia to industry, by collaboration or via employees
6. Contributions to open-source projects and standardization, providing access to the framework and encouraging its broad adoption in commercial and public systems for interested parties.

The consortium has identified a series of general exploitation points as a prelude to each individual partner's exploitation strategy.

3.1 Academic Exploitation plan

This characteristically includes the offering of courses and seminars with topics related to the project. Through that, the project can attract researchers and new students to work on and improve the ideas of the project. Another area of focus for the academic partners within FEMaLe is the exploitation of their work and project results through contributions to open-source software, particularly the digital tools, as a major outcome of the project.

Its maintenance presents an equally important objective to ensure that the results of FEMaLe will remain available and relevant long after the project terminates. This will be supported by building and engaging a developer community around FEMaLe. The community will form a foundation for further research and development in the area of healthcare IT services, incorporating cybersecurity.

The availability of the FEMaLe framework is expected to be a valuable asset for all academic partners in terms of building new partnerships, engaging in future projects and acquiring further funding at the national and EU level.

3.2 Citizen-Arena Exploitation plan

Acceleration through public sector and not-for-profit partnerships will be driven by the civil society organisations to contribute to exploitation of FEMaLe results by raising awareness across their networks mainly in the healthcare arena, addressing, in particular, the lack of awareness of citizens of the benefits of taking measures towards transition to digital-based healthcare services. Through planned engagement these partners will be able to connect the needs of healthcare services with the specific capabilities of the project solutions and forge relationships with early adopters and the digital tools at large – a key resource for exploitation.

3.3 Business Exploitation plan

To achieve the envisioned impacts, the FEMaLe innovative solutions developed under WP4-WP7 will provide competitive advantage while enlarging the market footprint, knowledge base and services portfolio of the companies involved. Hence, a platform of healthcare technologies, products and services will be generated for exploitation by EU companies.

The engagement activities under WP9 will, in addition to ensuring healthcare agents informed perspectives, will raise awareness of the benefits of implementing sustainable digital-based measures across a diverse spectrum of agents. This will establish trust and form a valuable cohort of early adopters to accelerate the exploitation of the results in the EU.

To unify the consortium behind a common vision for exploitation of the results, FEMaLe leverages the knowledge of the consortium to identify and stratify opportunities for the anticipated outcomes, inform innovation priorities and explore and plan healthcare services systems and undertake commercial assessment and planning including collaboration or where necessary joint-venture agreements to prepare the path for innovation and exploitation beyond the project.

A comprehensive exploitation plan is developed outlining the exploitation activities to be performed within and beyond the project, the priority healthcare agents and spheres best suited to exploit the results of FEMaLe and the measures that will be used to assess effectiveness on an on-going basis.

The exploitation plan will be consistent with the terms of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement ensuring there is a clear pathway exploiting project outputs and will contain the following elements: exploitation objectives, internal processes to collate and manage knowledge outputs, to ensure full use of all FEMaLe results, identification and profiling of use cases for the innovations, proposed tools and channels for transfer knowledge, ensuring effective exploitation of the project outputs, processes to ensure foreground and Intellectual Property (IP) are properly managed.

FEMaLe's exploitation plan is developed by SWU within WP 9 – Deliverable 9.5 – Exploitation of results plan an implementation with contribution from all WP leaders and other partners.